

FROM TRADITIONAL TO DIGITAL CLASSROOMS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES OF INSTRUCTIONAL TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

The primary goal of the research was to determine how the teachers were changing back and forth between digital and traditional learning in tertiary learning. The researchers conducted the study using the qualitative research methodology, and this was carried out on the paradigm of interpretivism. The sample was teachers at the Faculty of Education, from Sindh University and University of Sufism and Modern Sciences, Bhitshah, Sindh. By convenience sampling, seven teachers were chosen to be the participants. The semi-structured interviews were used to obtain data, and the process went on until saturation occurred. The data obtained were investigated by conducting thematic analysis to determine major themes. The key results indicated that the educators experienced a number of challenges in the transition, such as a deficiency of training, technical problems, low bandwidth, electricity failure and institutional support. Despite the apparent positive effect of the digital tools, which purportedly increased engagement and flexibility, the teaching methods remained largely traditional among many teachers, suggesting the lack of equalization of the pedagogical change. The results also indicated that digital competence by teachers was relevant to the adoption of digital approaches in teaching. The researchers have arrived at the conclusion that the perception of teachers, their skills, and institutional support has an effect on technological transformation. It is advised that universities should come up with explicit policies, offer ongoing training, and advance digital infrastructures to facilitate effective adoption of digital teaching.

Keywords: Digital transformation, Instructional transformation, Teachers' experiences, Technology integration, Diffusion of innovations

INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation has already been a characteristic element of the modern system of education, and it transforms the organisation of teaching and learning under various conditions

(OECD, 2021). The dawn of digital tools, platforms, and learning management systems has diverted education from the traditional, teacher-centred practice into more flexible and technology-mediated practices (Bitar and

Davidovich, 2024). Such a shift is not just technical but a pedagogical one because it necessitates some deep-rooted changes in the ways in which knowledge is transmitted, learned, and communicated in the classrooms (Consoli et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the success of such transformation is highly determined by the manner in which the teachers perceive these changes and apply them in their teaching methods (Akram et al., 2022).

On the global level, studies point to the fact that digital technologies may create a greater level of engagement, personalization of learning, and efficiency in instruction, but their assimilation is not uniform and multifaceted (UNESCO, 2023). These issues are more acute in developing countries like Pakistan because of the infrastructural restrictions, lack of professional training, and the unwillingness of educators to change (Aidoo and Chebure, 2024). In colleges and universities, the shift to online classes is still dynamic in nature, and teachers are the key mediating factor in the transition (Fernández-Batanero et al., 2021). Even though there is a focus on policy towards digitalisation, the actual concerns of transforming teaching practices are under-researched in the local settings.

Technology integration and digital competence have been studied in existing literature, but much of this fall into quantitative or survey research, which, to date, deals with the levels of adoption but not lived experiences (Zhao et al., 2021). Research usually ignores the subtle dynamics of how teachers live through, negotiate, and are modified by digital transformation in their teaching life (Alberola-Mulet et al., 2021). Moreover, on the one hand, systematic reviews present general information about the trend, and on the other hand, they do not reflect context-related problems to educators in developing areas (Lopez-Nuñez et al., 2024). This provides a big gap in comprehending the way of instructional change experience at the micro level, especially within the Faculty of Education at Sindh University.

The issue that is considered in this paper is the narrow scope of the qualitative research on the experience of teachers in switching between traditional and digital classrooms from a local Pakistani perspective. Devoid of these insights,

there is a danger that the policy and practice will lack inclusivity in the classroom application experiences. Thus, the proposed study will examine the lived experiences of the teachers in relation to the instructional transformation with the emphasis on the challenges, adaptations, and the pedagogical changes in this transformation.

This study is justified by the idea that it is necessary to go deeper into the analysis of technology adoption rather than analyze it superficially. Instant agents of instructional change are teachers, whose beliefs, competencies, and practices have a direct impact on the success of the digital transformation (Guillén Gámez et al., 2024). By emphasizing the teachers over students, a more significant study of digital tools as a part of pedagogy can be conducted. A qualitative approach would be especially suitable because it would allow exploring the perceptions, realities, and experiences of the context that cannot be quantified (Cena et al., 2024). Semi-structured interviews can also be recommended by this method as they are flexible to identify additional, detailed aspects of what instructional change can bring (Naz et al., 2022).

Research Aim and Objectives

The purpose of this research is to investigate the experiences of teachers who have moved their teaching to digital classrooms in the Faculty of Education at the University of Sindh. The study seeks to understand how teachers view instructional change. It also examines the difficulties they face and the ways they implement digital technologies in their teaching.

- To investigate the views of the teachers on the process of the transition between traditional and digital teaching practices.
- To determine the issues teachers, encounter during instructional change.
- To investigate what measures are applied by teachers to conform to the environment of digital teaching.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Traditional vs Digital Teaching

Traditional instruction has always involved teacher-centered instruction, with knowledge

being delivered in a systematic and managed classroom atmosphere (Bitar and Davidovich, 2024). In this type, the teacher is the authority in the content delivery, and the student tends to play an active role only in receiving the material that the teacher provides, which may limit their ability to think and learn. Digital learning format, on the contrary, encourages learners through an approach that is more interactive and student-centred, making it possible to learn content via numerous platforms and resources (OECD, 2021). This change is indicative of a greater rise of change in education because information is not as closed off as it only existed in the classroom, since it is now available online.

However, the replacement of traditional with digital teaching is not necessarily a good and easy process. On the one hand, it can make the teaching more flexible and more accessible; on the other hand, there is a risk to the current practice, and educators will be forced to alter a considerable amount (Consoli et al., 2023). Some research states that digital instruction increases the level of engagement and learning, whereas in other works, technology is said to substitute the old-fashioned method with the use of technology without any actual innovation unless the pedagogical strategy is proper (Akram et al., 2022). It means that the traditional and the digital process of teaching do not differ because of technology only, but it is a highly grounded challenge that deals with pedagogy.

In developing countries, traditional and digital methods often co-exist. Teachers must balance conventional and new technologies in a hybrid environment (UNESCO, 2023). This duality often creates inconsistency. Examining how change happens in practice is necessary, rather than assuming it is linear.

Technology Integration in Education

The theme of technology integration in education has been excellently debated as one of the reasons behind the improvement of instruction, but its application has been complicated and uneven in contexts (Zhao et al., 2021). However, the concept of integration is not usually determined by the presence of digital tools but by their practical incorporation into the learning process in order to

maximize its end results (Consoli et al., 2023). Nevertheless, numerous investigations demonstrate that technology is commonly applied on a surface level, where it is used to complement the already existing teaching strategies but does not necessarily change them (Akram et al., 2022). This means that the theoretical possibilities of digital technologies and their practical use in the classroom are not matched.

It has also been suggested in research that the digital competence of teachers is a significant factor in successful integration since the lack of skills and confidence might result in poor use of technology (Fernández-Batanero et al., 2021). Although the frameworks note the necessity to integrate technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, empirical data points to the fact that in practice, teachers are not always able to balance this (Zeng et al., 2022). Further, institutional aspects like training avenues, infrastructures, and policy endorsement also play a key role in determining the level of technology integration (Aidoo and Chebure, 2024).

Meanwhile, certain researchers claim that paying too much attention to technology is a danger, and the quality of pedagogy will be neglected, which will result in the overuse of digital means without explicit educational potential (López-Nuñez et al., 2024). This criticism indicates that the integration of technology cannot be considered as positive, but it has to be made under a critical analysis in a certain teaching scenario. Hence, it is necessary to learn how educators perceive and use technology in practice in a classroom to be able to judge its real contribution to education.

Teachers' Experiences and Challenges

The experiences of teachers are the core of assessing the achievements or failures of the digital transformation in the field of education because they have to introduce new instructional practices (Korhonen et al., 2024). Studies show that this change is usually accompanied by several difficulties, such as insufficient training, institutional support, and additional workload to handle because of their learning about new technologies (Aydin et al., 2024). Such challenges may result in resistance or partial adoption,

especially when the teachers are unprepared or unassisted in the virtual worlds.

Besides that, the convictions and the attitude of teachers to technology also play a significant role in determining their readiness to incorporate digital technologies into practice (Alberola-Mulet et al., 2021). Although technology is seen to be a chance to improve the learning process by some educators, others see technology as a distraction to the old ways of teaching, which has created a conflict between innovation and tradition. This difference makes it crucial to consider personal experience instead of making generalizations about how people would react to digital transformation.

Furthermore, it has been indicated that the contextual factors, including institutional culture and policy frameworks, influence the development of teachers' digital agency, alongside personal competence (Peretti et al., 2024). Digital teaching strategies require the teacher to have proper technical skills, but external restrictions can reduce their capacity to implement the strategies fully. This suggests that it is not only the individual issues that cause challenges, but they are integrated into systems of education.

Pedagogical Transformation

Pedagogical transformation is one of the main elements of a transition between conventional and digital classrooms since not only the tools but also the methods of teaching and learning change (Bitar and Davidovich, 2024). Online learning promotes student-centred learning where teachers are facilitators and not the only sources of knowledge, and encourages cooperation, critical thinking and self-learning (OECD, 2021). But this is not possible to come about with the availability of technology, but rather a redesigning of instructional design and classroom practices.

It has been found that a large number of educators cannot go beyond the use of digital tools, and their methods of teaching online remain conventional, without any substantial alteration in the teaching methodology (Akram et al., 2022). This implies that technology as a system will not result in transformation unless it is supplemented by changes in teaching beliefs and practices. In addition, the idea of pedagogical change is

idealized in the literature, and the practical challenges teachers have to cope with during the adoption of new strategies are minimal (Guillén Gámez et al., 2024).

Meanwhile, certain works also provide some favourable results of digital pedagogy, such as the ability to improve flexibility and personalized learning (Zhao et al., 2021). Nevertheless, these advantages do not always manifest themselves in various settings, especially in areas that have fewer resources or training (Aidoo and Chebure, 2024). This implies that pedagogical change is not even and situational.

Research Gap

Despite the excellent information offered in the current literature on the topic of digital teaching and the use of technologies, there is still a major lack of information on the lived experiences of teachers in particular settings. Most of the studies are based on quantitative approaches, which do not investigate teacher-adaptation in instruction but rely on the measurement of the levels of technology utilization (Zhao et al., 2021). Moreover, the research can be highly general in character and leaves out the contextual issues that do not apply in developing countries like Pakistan (UNESCO, 2023).

Another area of work that is barely seen is research conducted by looking at instructional change through a qualitative lens, especially in institutions of higher learning in Sindh. Although the literature on digital competence and pedagogical change addresses it, it can seldom accurately reflect the subtle experiences, issues, and strategies of teachers throughout the transition process (Korhonen et al., 2024). Such absence of context-related qualitative data signifies the necessity of an extensive study aiming at the attitudes of teachers. Thus, the current research aims to fill the mentioned gap and examine instructional change by conducting semi-structured interviews with educators at the Faculty of Education of the University of Sindh.

Theoretical Framework

The present research is informed by Diffusion of Innovations Theory, which provides the process of spreading new ideas and technologies through a

social system over a period of time. This study considers the digital teaching practices as an innovation and the social system, which is the Faculty of Education at the University of Sindh. The theory is of special concern since such an instructional change does not take place evenly, as the teachers embrace digital solutions at varying paces, based on their perceptions, capabilities, and their institutional setting. The studies show that the adoption of technologies in education depends on several interdependent issues, and not only on access to digital resources, which confirms the applicability of the diffusion theory to the analysis of this discrepancy (Galimova et al., 2024). The theory is aligned with the major variables such as innovation, channels of communication, time,

and social system as a composite of variables explaining how the process of adoption goes. It is also further operationalized by taking five attributes that include relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. These variables are critical in this study as it is more likely that the teachers will consider adopting digital teaching when they think it is beneficial and in line with their teaching style, and can be easily dealt with in practice. Nevertheless, there are some indicators that perceived complexity and absence of observable benefits often demoralize full uptake, especially in environments with a limited amount of training and assistance (Akram et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Diffusion of Innovations framework showing how innovation attributes shape teachers' perceptions, adoption decisions, and implementation of digital teaching

Also, the theory identifies adopters into innovators, early adopters and laggards; some of these categories possess variance in readiness and willingness to change. This classification can help understand why certain teachers are interested in embracing digital transformation and some still resist it. Most recent studies also maintain that we can also adopt based on trust, perceived value, and institutional readiness as opposed to technology per se, particularly in developing education

systems (UNESCO, 2023). Hence, Diffusion of innovations Theory is the appropriate theory to understand the way of how teachers feel and react towards digital transformation in this research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper was based on a qualitative research design based on the approach of interpretivism to examine the experiences of teachers in transforming instructional teaching methods in

traditional classes to digital classes. It was deemed that a qualitative approach would be suitable in that it enables the in-depth analysis of perceptions, meanings, and the lived experience of participants, which are not well explored using the quantitative approach (Cena et al., 2024). The interpretivist paradigm is one that reality is constructed through social means and, thus, the experiences of digital transformation among teachers are constituted by the unique context, beliefs, and interactions within the educational setting (Lochmiller, 2021). This method allowed the study to go beyond the superficial analysis and analyze how teachers perceive and react to the digital change in their teaching methodology.

The study was carried out at Faculty of education from University of Sindh, and University of Sufism and Modern Sciences, Bhitshah. The sample was chosen through convenience sampling, where seven respondents were considered to be reached by the researcher because they were at the right place to respond to the study. Although convenience sampling is not always described as generalizable, in qualitative research where the focus is to obtain rich and context-oriented information instead of findings that are generalizable, it is deemed adequate (Naz et al., 2022). Sampling was continued until a saturation point was reached, at which no new themes and meaningful lessons were derived with more interviews, and hence, sufficient depth and adequacy of data.

Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data, ensuring that there was flexibility in the type of data collected without disturbing the participants with the aim of the interview. This approach helped the respondents share their opinion freely, and it also gave the researcher an opportunity to dig deeper into other pertinent issues as they arose (Naz et al., 2022). To reduce the possibility of subjecting the respondents to undue exhaustion, each interview lasted about 20 to 30 minutes, and this was adequate to ensure that the interviewer collected relevant answers to the questions asked. It has been established that semi-structured interviews are effective for qualitative researchers to capture delicate views and contextual facts.

Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data collected, and this method identifies patterns and themes in qualitative data used. Thematic analysis has been chosen because it is flexible and befits interpreting complex data in a systematic manner (Braun and Clarke, 2023). This method included data familiarisation, coding, theme emergence, and interpretation so that impressive information got revealed as the narratives of the participants unfolded. When taken systematically, the method also promotes the transparency and rigour of qualitative research (Lochmiller, 2021). The matter of ethics was well considered in the course of the research. Before the data collection process, informed consent of the participants was taken, and they were made aware of the intent of the research. All data were taken care of in a secure way to guarantee confidentiality and anonymity since no identities of the participants were disclosed. Qualitative research must have these practices of ethics as a means of preserving trust and safeguarding the rights of the participants (Cena et al., 2024).

FINDINGS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Theme 1: Transition Challenges in Digital Teaching

The results showed that the teachers had to face several issues in the process of changing conventional classrooms to digital, especially the issue of training and technical problems. The majority of interviewees emphasized that the transition was abrupt and they had to change without appropriate training. This raised some confusion, and this impacted their belief in using digital tools efficiently. Indicatively, even in the case of Participant 2, he indicated that, as there were instructions to use digital platforms, there was no appropriate training, and he needed to acquire all the knowledge independently. The reaction is an indication of a larger problem in which the expectations of institutions were not supported with proper mechanisms.

Likewise, Participant 5 was interpreting it by saying, sometimes some tools come in handy, and technical issues consume time and interrupt the teaching process. This shows the fact that, the technical barriers do not only impact the capacity of teachers to present the content but also creates

an interruption in the classroom interaction. These issues were not just due to skills, but went ahead to infrastructural constraints such as the presence of poor internet connectivity and access to digital materials.

The other significant issue that was realized was resistance to change, especially amongst teachers who were more content with traditional teaching methods. Participant 7 mentioned that he found traditional teaching to be more dependable since online techniques are not always convenient to control. This implies that the resistance was not necessarily caused by unwillingness but was under the influence of the perceived complexity and uncertainty in online space.

Most importantly, the results show that these issues should not be viewed independently of each other. The insufficiency of training also caused technical issues and, in turn, strengthened the resistance and lowered the drive to engage in digital practices in teaching. However, as some respondents were able to admit the advantages of digital tools, the transition experience was reported to be stressful and taxing. This indicates that the problem is not merely the use of technology but the willingness of an individual and of an institution to help it bring significant change. Thus, the transition problems that can be faced by teachers indicate more structural and pedagogical problems that have to be tackled to bring about successful digital transformation.

Theme 2: Pedagogical Transformation and Changing Teaching Practices

The results showed that digital change has had an impact on teaching methods, specifically in an attempt to change the teacher-centred approach into a more student-centred one. This change was, however, not uniform among participants. Other teachers claimed that digital tools enabled teachers to interact with students in a more active way, whereas others continued to use traditional methods even in a digital environment. As an illustration, Participant 1 said, “Digital tools assist students in being more engaged since they can ask questions and interact without any difficulties.” This shows a good attitude towards digital teaching as a way of improving the level of engagement and interaction.

Participant 4, in turn, clarified that I would give people the explanation to do everything and leave students alone because students rely on the instructions too much. This shows that even though digital materials were available, there were teachers who were still teacher-centred, implying that the beliefs about pedagogy are critical in influencing the practice of instruction.

It was also found that digital teaching demanded that the teacher redesign the lesson planning and delivery techniques. Participant 3 added that teaching digitally does not only require the usage of tools, but it also alters the lesson planning and classroom management. This points to the fact that instructional change is about more than just integrating new technologies as a form of change in pedagogy.

Nevertheless, this change had a positive impact on not all the participants. Others raised apprehensions regarding having less control of the classroom and the inability to keep the students attentive. Participant 6 pointed out that, in online classes, the students cannot be sure that the other students are listening. This implies that though digital teaching has some chances of engagement, it also poses some new problems in classroom management.

On the whole, the results show that pedagogical change is a slow and discontinuous process. As much as digital tools can promote more interactive and student-centred learning, they are only effective as long as the teachers make changes in their teaching practices. The fact that the experiences of the participants were varied indicates that the process of instructional transformation depends on personal styles of teaching, degree of confidence, and attitude towards digital teaching, as opposed to being the natural consequence of using technology.

Theme 3: Digital Competence, Support, and Perceived Impact on Teaching

Results have identified that computer competence of the teachers and the intensity of institutional help had a dramatic effect on the teachers' experiences of digital teaching. Those who were more confident about using digital tools had more positive experiences, whereas the participants with lower competencies were frustrated and hesitant.

An example is like Participant 2 mentioned, in his response to the question, that teaching would be simpler and more efficient once you know how to apply the tools. This indicates that competence is instrumental in influencing the attitude of teachers towards digital teaching.

Participant 5 also said, I am not yet sure about utilizing some of the digital tools, and, therefore, I do not use them in my classes. This is a sign of failure because of incompetence that can lead to biased or partial adoption of technology. These results indicate that digital competence is not just an issue of a technical nature, but it is also connected to the degree of confidence and willingness to test a new mode of doing things.

The other factor of importance was institutional support. Some respondents pointed to the lack of a structured training program and on-the-job training. Participant 3 replied, "Proper workshops should be conducted in order to train teachers; otherwise, adjustment becomes challenging." This implies that the transition will be implementable only to its own limitation since the teachers will have to handle the transition without the support of institutions.

Nevertheless, the majority of respondents admitted that they found digital teaching to positively influence their professional teaching in case of its effective utilization. Participant 1 said that digital tools can be used to clarify concepts better and make the lesson more engaging. Nonetheless, over-dependence on technology was also noted by some of the participants. Participant 7 said, when over reliance on digital tools is done, it can impair the ability of students to think. This expresses an urgent conflict between the advantages and the possible disadvantages of net-teaching.

Altogether, the results indicate that the effects of digital transformation are not homogeneous, but they rely on the collaboration of competence, support, and perception. With support and confidence, teachers tend to engage in digital practices with greater effectiveness, and those who lack these aspects may either oppose or restrict their utilization. It means that digital transformation may be successful only with the combination of technical matters, in the case of

the necessity of constant professional growth and institutional dedication.

DISCUSSION

Results of the given study contain significant information on how educators go through the process of the classroom becoming digital and are subject to a critical understanding in terms of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory. The outcomes indicate that implementation of digital practices in the teaching area is not homogeneous but instead differs depending on the perception of the teachers relative to the important innovation attributes, including relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. This reinforces the fact that the adoption of technology in the education sector is more of a perception and context-dependent activity rather than one that is dependent on access (Galimova et al., 2024).

The role of complexity as a key variable in the diffusion theory is closely manifested in the first theme, which is transition challenges. Respondents have indicated that the challenges associated with the absence of training and technical challenges have indicated that digital instruction was viewed as intricate and challenging to handle. The diffusion theory states that the greater the perceived complexity, the lower the adoption chances, because people prefer not to engage in real change that involves making a great effort or learning new skills. This is in line with the past studies that have indicated that teachers tend to have difficulties with technology integration in cases where there is a lack of proper support and training (Akram et al., 2022). The results also prove that complexity is not technical only, but also pedagogical, since educators have to respond in their instructional strategy to the study of learning new tools. This supports the notion that there are multidimensional aspects of adoption barriers and not necessarily technological.

Meanwhile, the findings also highlight the contribution of the relative advantage, in which some of the involved participants disclosed that electronic instruments increased interaction and instructional competency. It means that educators are more willing to apply digital practices when they get an impression of conspicuous benefits. It

matches the literature in which it is assumed that perceived usefulness is among the leading intentions of using technology in learning settings (OECD, 2021). But the findings also indicate that perceived benefits are not necessarily enough to make adoption possible in the presence of other impediments, including complexity and the absence of support. This implies that innovation attributes are not independent and have each other, hence a more holistic comprehension of diffusion processes is encouraged.

The second one, pedagogical transformation, can be directly related to the aspect of compatibility in the diffusion theory. The results indicate that there were teachers who adjusted to student-centred teaching matters, whilst others persisted in using traditional methodologies of teaching in the digital environment. This implies that the adoption will be based on the perception of digital teaching as being compatible with the current beliefs and teaching styles. The more teachers saw the digital tools in terms of being compatible with their pedagogical values, the more likely they were to integrate them, and the more they perceived a blend, the more resistant they became. Such observation is reinforced by the study that demonstrates that teachers' beliefs and choice of instruction play a role in the integration of technology instead of technology itself (Alberola-Mulet et al., 2021).

Moreover, the asymmetrical character of pedagogical change is a manifestation of adopter-types suggested in diffusion theory. There are those who may be viewed as early adopters who were active users of digital tools, and others who belong to the late majority or laggards who were unresponsive or opposed to change. This difference confirms the theoretical argument that people implement innovations at varying levels according to his/her preparedness and ensure (UNESCO, 2023). The results thus support the relevance of diffusion theory to rapidly understand the teacher disparities on digital transformation.

The third theme, which is digital competence and institutional support, brings about the relevance of trialability and observability. According to the participants, the possibilities to explore digital tools and see their positive features affected their

desire to implement them. Educational leaders were more inclined to adopt a digital method when they could see positive effects, such as lesson delivery or the level of student engagement. This confirms the theoretical perspective that the innovations become more easily accepted in cases where the outcomes can be observed and tested on a smaller level (Akram et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the results also indicate that the lack of training opportunities decreased trialability, which further lowered the adoption. This implies that institutional factors are important in facilitating or inhibiting the diffusion process.

Moreover, the results of the studies reveal that communication channels and social systems, which are major components of the diffusion theory, have a significant effect on adoption. There is no ongoing formal training and organization of the training, which indicates poor communication in the school environment. The diffusion theory highlights that successful communication is critical in the dissemination of innovation, where people will be guided by information and experiences shared by other people to make decisions on adoption. The lack of the mentioned support mechanisms could be one of the reasons why some teachers were not so willing, even after seeing the possible benefits of digital teaching. This aligns with the research that revealed that the institutional environment and peer support are the key points of technology adoption (Aidoo and Chebure, 2024).

One more significant factor that has become evident due to the results is the role of time in the process of adoption. The findings indicate that teaching change is not a quick process but a process that has to be adjusted to, and not changed instantly. Those teachers who were initially resistant to the appearance of digital teaching can learn to embrace it in the course of time with experience and confidence. This advocates the viewpoint of the spread theory that adoption is a process and not a one-time experience, and it is a process where some stages are encompassed, which include awareness, interest, evaluation, trial, and implementation (Zhao et al., 2021).

More importantly, the results also contradict overly optimistic perceptions of digital transformation in some of the literature. Although

past literature states that technology can improve learning, this research proves that these are not always expected and require various situations, encouragement, and instructor preparation (López-Nuñez et al., 2024). This indicates that digital transformation cannot be considered to be necessarily isolating but must be assessed with seriousness, with references to realities on the ground.

In general, the results of this research have much to contribute to the support of Diffusion of Innovations Theory since the themes discovered can be compared to its key variables and concepts. But the findings also caution that the theory should be perceived on a contextualised basis, especially in the case of developing education systems in which structural and institutional obstacles have a great role to play. The study thus fills the existing literature with the qualitative evidence on the functioning of diffusion processes in the context of higher education in Sindh, in which the teacher perception, institutional support, and situational determinants of digital transformation are significant.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current paper will elaborate on the experiences of teachers who have been transferred between digital and traditional classrooms. The change in instructions is a complicated and disproportionate procedure, which relies on numerous factors. The study discovered that even though digital teaching has favorable aspects, there are also drawbacks, such as the absence of training, technological problems, and change resistance. The research found that pedagogical change did not come automatically; a majority of the teachers continue to employ the archaic approaches when using digital tools. Digital capability of teachers and the institutional support had significant influence on the success of the digital instructional practice. The paper brings in the qualitative context-specific information of the industry of higher education in Sindh with special focus on what teachers think and how much they have experienced in the process of digital transformation.

These findings are used to give some of the recommendations. To start with, the institutions

that are proposed will provide systematic and continuous tough training courses to turn the educators into computer-literate and confident individuals. Second, efficient policy frameworks should be arranged, which may facilitate through the introduction of digital technologies into the teaching process that will allow maintaining the ratio between the expectation and support provided by the institution. Third, is the digital infrastructure that is supposed to be invested, being an effective infrastructural variable will reduce the technological barrier and make the teaching process more fruitful. Finally, the institutions will have to instil a culture of learning among the educators that will assist them in disseminating the best practices and improving their acclimatization to the digital teaching model in a slow and gradual way. It means that the measures can assure the changes in instruction to become more efficient and permanent.

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